

THE VILLAGE LIBRARY OF ROLE CHANGING CITIZENS' BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

Libraries play a role as institutions that provide sources of knowledge for the community which are expected to inspire readers to carry out social change. This research aims to analyze changes in residents' behavior through village library activities. This research was conducted in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency using qualitative methods. Data was collected by interviews and field observations. Data were analyzed using an interpretive qualitative approach. The Pajukukang Village Government manages the Al-Iqra village library which later received an award as a Transformative Village. This research indicates the village library of role changing citizens' behavior by becoming active livestock breeder. Active residents read in the library and gain knowledge about raising ducks. Village libraries make residents have the capacity to change their socio-economic behavior to be more productive.

Keywords: Library, Village, Social Change, Livestock Breeders.

INTRODUCTION

A library is a room, part of a building or a separate building that contains a collection of books, which are arranged and arranged in such a way that they are easy to find and use if needed by the reader at any time. Libraries have a strategic role in educating the lives of the nation's children, both in developed and developing countries. The existence of libraries is a necessity in the progress of civilisation and human culture. Libraries are centres of information, science, technology, art and culture. Libraries can function as a vehicle for education, research, preservation, information, and recreation to improve the intelligence and empowerment of the nation. The policy to advance the world of libraries in Indonesia is considered the most realistic option as a vehicle for lifelong learning to develop the potential of the community in order to become a human being who believes and is devoted to God Almighty, has noble character, is healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and becomes a democratic and responsible citizen in supporting the implementation of National education [1].

Regulation of the Head of the National Library of the Republic of Indonesia Number 21 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Social Inclusion-Based Librarianship Education and Training that social inclusion-based libraries are expected to be able to become a forum for the community to find life solutions in improving the quality of life both socially and economically. Social inclusion-based library transformation is one of the priority policies initiated by the central government through the National Planning and Development Agency (Bappenas) and the National Library of the Republic of Indonesia. This policy focuses on village libraries in all districts/cities in Indonesia.

According to Prasyesti, Koko, & Rahma (2021), this programme is intended to improve the welfare of the community, especially people in rural areas by strengthening literacy. Libraries as a source of community information are expected to actively participate in strengthening literacy [2]. Apart from providing various types of library collections that suit the needs of the community, libraries can also be a place to learn together, discuss, network, and hold special programmes that can increase community empowerment. For example, training in making contemporary handicrafts that have the potential to be marketed, holding workshops on agriculture, animal husbandry, or digital business, and other training tailored to the needs and conditions of the local community. So that the community will have sufficient knowledge, adequate skills (soft skills), to support economic empowerment towards prosperity.

To meet the challenges of development, the transformation of services based on social inclusion is imperative for libraries. Library services must be accessible to all levels of society. Library transformation based on social inclusion can be interpreted in the perspective of national development as a cultural strategy to realise a literate society through collective movements that are mass, widespread, and national in scale. Literacy and literate society are the culmination of a long process of education, both formal and non-formal education pursued by the community. Libraries play a role as institutions that provide information needed by the community. To be able to play this role, there must be strengthening of library institutions. Strengthening the library has a big impact on social strengthening of the community by forming a literate society [3].

Some previous researchers related to this research are as follows. First, research conducted by Kusnendar 2019 on social changes in village communities after the existence of broiler chicken farming in Dengok IV Hamlet, Dengok Village, Playen District, Gunungkidul Regency. The results of this study show that the process of broiler farming in Dengok Village is influenced by several internal factors such as dissatisfaction with the existing situation, the ability of financial capital, the open attitude of the community towards innovation and limited knowledge of the impact of livestock waste; and external factors such as government policies on partnership models in broiler farming, core farming companies, and the existence of financial institutions providing capital credit.

While the social changes identified in this study can be classified into three divisions, namely: The first phase of change, which includes several changes such as changes in the norm system, shifts in social status, and social behaviour; The second phase of change, social change that occurs is marked by several changes such as: the emergence of broiler farming as a new economic institution in Dengok Village, the development of the norm system and the emergence of breeders as a new social group, livelihood shifts, changes in social organisation patterns and changes in economic orientation; and The third phase of change is marked by the development of regulations regarding broiler farming, changes in breeder behaviour, changes in the socio-economic structure of broiler breeders.

The second study was conducted by Salamah 2020 which looked at the effect of agricultural and livestock technology policies on social change in improving the welfare of farmers/ranchers. The research revealed the influence of agricultural technology policies and programs on changes in the attitudes and behaviour of farmers, as well as the dynamics of farmer groups in improving the business activities/welfare levels of farmers and breeders. The research design used was analytical descriptive survey

method. This method aims to obtain a description of the symptoms studied in the current situation, and on that basis, then find answers for solving problems or symptoms that exist. Based on the results of the study, it was revealed that the implementation of the technology development programme carried out by the Nuclear Engineering Research and Development Center of BATAN (Indonesian Nuclear Energy Agency) for the farmer / livestock community in the research area, in the context of social change, requires good conditions in terms of extension and communication, to farmers / livestock farmers need to instill motivation and ability to use and disseminate technological innovations through farmer groups, and it is necessary to strengthen the cohesiveness of farmer groups through improving group elements, namely group goals, group structure, group atmosphere and climate, diversity and group functions and tasks, group effectiveness, group maintenance and development.

The third research is Djoh (2020) related to the impact of modernisation on social change on farming communities in Kambata Tana Village, East Sumba Regency This study aims to determine the impact of modernisation on social changes in farming communities in Kambata Tana Village, Pandawai District, East Sumba Regency. The results showed that there were changes in the mindset and behaviour of the people of Kambata Tana village, on the one hand accepting the presence of modernisation in agriculture, but on the other hand they still uphold their cultural values and local wisdom. Agricultural transformation that occurs is only limited to production methods without changing the social structure of the community. Agricultural modernisation has led to a reduction in the need for labour.

Human and animal labour can be replaced by modern machines such as tractors, water pumps, corn and rice drying machines. Marx's prediction about the formation of capitalist production capital is not proven in the Kambata Tana village community. The concept of ownership of means of production still maintains the existing tradition. Ownership of the means of production is based on community ownership, so that no one party will become the master of the means of production. The farming community of Kambata Tana village generally prioritises a social-community orientation, which is realised by the tradition of gotong royong in their activities [4].

The fourth study was conducted by Siahaan 2011 who analysed the existence of libraries as part of human civilisation and culture towards changes in life. Libraries as institutions or those tasked with storing, processing, packaging, and distributing information are currently required to be able to adapt to meet user needs in a relevant, accurate and precise manner. Librarians as information workers act as agents of reform bringing librarianship innovation. Librarians are required to be able to anticipate technological advances in disseminating information that brings changes to the people who use the library so that it will be seen starting from mentality and morals, ways of thinking, speaking then in real actions or actions. In the end, people are more dynamic, critical, analytically active and innovative.

One segment of the community that benefits from social inclusion-based library services in Maros Regency is livestock farmers in Pajukukang Village. Based on the background of the above problems, this study aims to analyse how the role of the Pajukukang Village library in Maros Regency changes the behaviour of livestock farmers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Changes in Citizen Behaviour

The Pajukukang Maros community is advanced where everyone works according to their expertise and depends on each other, the existence of norms and laws that have been mutually agreed upon between communities, the formation of ties on the basis of profession or work, relationships between people based on interests. Changes in the structure of the farming community in Pajukukang from previously raising livestock combined with other livestock along with advances in communication, science and technology, and various information that enters rural areas are able to change the institutional structure and social system of the village. The village social system which may have previously been very exclusive and closed due to the influence of culture and customs of the ancestors is gradually changing and the people of Pajukukang Village are able to adjust to the various developments of the times and foreign influences from outside.

Changes in structures, social systems, values, attitudes of mini are elements of social change in society both shared by the community in Pajukukang Village individually and together in a social system incorporated in a social inclusion-based library. After the existence of an inclusion-based library, some of the local people have started separating livestock, selling, choosing the right food for livestock, so that the livestock obtained is much more and from livestock products can help the local economy, it can be concluded that social behaviour in the community in Pajukukang Village after the existence of a social inclusion-based library, one of which is cooperation that is well established in the local community. This cooperation has also been established quite well and can be seen from the way the local community responds to mutual cooperation in cleaning cages, keeping livestock safe. The mutual assistance that the local community does, such as helping others who are in need of help. Thus, the cooperation established after the existence of this library fosters a sense of kinship among local communities and also fosters a sense of caring for others, both people who live around Pajukukang Village.

Social Inclusion-Based Literacy

Literacy is often simply defined as the ability to read and write or the condition of being literate as opposed to illiterate. A literate person is one who can both read and write with understanding. Literacy signifies that a person is educated if he or she can engage in activities where reading and writing are required to achieve effective functioning in the family, group and community. Reading literacy is an individual's capacity to understand, use and reflect on written texts to achieve his/her life goals and develop his/her knowledge and potential so that he/she can participate in society [5].

Literacy is the ability to access, understand and use something appropriately through reading, writing, listening or speaking. Another opinion states that literacy is a skill related to reading, writing and thinking that focuses on improving the ability to understand information critically, creatively and innovatively. Literacy is not just reading and writing but includes critical thinking skills utilising printed, visual and digital sources of knowledge [1]. Ontologically, the concept of literacy can be divided into several categories, namely: (1) Basic literacy is related to the ability to listen, speak, read, write and count, (2) Library Literacy is related to the delivery of understanding to distinguish reading materials that are fiction and non-fiction, to understand the use of catalogues and the application of collection codification, (3) Media Literacy which

relates to understanding the substance to framing of mass media¹, (4) Technology Literacy which relates to the ability to understand the existence and usefulness of technological devices, and (4) Visual Literacy which relates to advanced understanding between elements of media literacy and technological literacy. The ontological perspective shows that the interpretation and even the operational meaning of literacy has undergone a very significant development. Literacy does not stop at boring calistung activities for some people, but has developed into a more contextual understanding. Starting with activities related to the cognitive side of intelligence (ecommon sens), enlightenment of the affective side (taste) and can be reflected in empiric action (psychomotor) [6].

Encouraging increased literacy requires efforts to transform public libraries in Indonesia based on social inclusion. A social inclusion-based library is a library that facilitates the community in developing its potential by looking at cultural diversity, willingness to accept change, and offering business opportunities, protecting and fighting for culture and human rights [7]. The concept of social inclusion-based literacy is to build communities to be more open to other communities, increasing their participation in society. This is done through increasing opportunities, access to resources and respect for them. Furthermore, it will ultimately promote community dignity and individual self-reliance as key assets to achieve a better quality of life [8].

Social Inclusion Library

Indonesia's low reading culture is one of the strategic issues of national development that must be resolved, one of which is by developing libraries. The importance of the existence of libraries as a foundation in developing the reading culture of the community is because libraries are able to reach out to the lowest level of users in the smallest area. Indonesia's territory consisting of thousands of islands separated by oceans is a challenge for the central government in terms of equitable development. Therefore, the existence of libraries is very helpful for the government in taking care of the community, including in terms of developing a reading culture and literacy in the community. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), until 2018 there were 71,074 villages spread across the territory of Indonesia. Therefore, if the existence of this library is optimised, the problem of low reading culture will be resolved [6]. Until now, libraries have not been seen as a basic and important part of various elements of institutions and society. This is understandable considering that library services have not played an optimal role in touching aspects of social problems in society. The existence of libraries has not contributed to reducing social problems in the community [9]. According to Noor, (2019), public libraries have an obligation to provide inclusive information services, which do not discriminate against anyone from their inherent attributes such as age, ethnicity, gender, religion, nationality, language, and social status.

The library's strategy to maintain its existence is to transform the library. The transformation model that is now being developed by public libraries or village libraries is a social inclusion-based library, by making literacy strengthening programmes for community welfare and poverty alleviation. Social inclusion-based library transformation is also not only to maintain the existence of a library, but also a form of support carried out by the library to support the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) programme. As IFLA calls on all parties to make libraries in every part of the world a partner in national and regional development plans in each country and

encourage libraries to be included in national development plans for SDGs. The call from IFLA above makes libraries play an important role in improving the welfare of society through the availability of access to information services, as a centre for learning and community activities [10].

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by the research subject, for example behaviour, perceptions, motivations, actions, and so on. This qualitative research process involves efforts such as asking questions and collecting specific data from participants, analysing data. This qualitative research process involves efforts such as asking questions and collecting specific data from participants, analysing data. Another reason this research uses the descriptive method is because it wants to analyse in depth the role of the village library in changing the behaviour of farmer breeders in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency. The research will be conducted in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency. This research will be conducted for 2 (two) months, namely August to September 2023. The selection of informants in research is important to explore data and information as well as knowledge to collect real and specific cases, actions or events [11]. Research informants are people who are sources of data in qualitative research who are considered to be able to provide the information needed for research purposes. The method used in taking samples using snowball sampling technique is a method for identifying, selecting and taking informants in a network or chain of continuous relationships. In determining informants, first one or two informants are selected as key informants, but because these two samples do not feel complete with the data provided, the researcher looks for other people who are considered to know more and can complement the data provided by the previous two samples. And so on, so that the number of samples is increasing [12]. The research data were analysed using the interpretative qualitative method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Behaviour change itself is a shift or development in the social structure of society which consists of forward or backward changes. Forward change is the development of circumstances that have a good impact and progress in society. Meanwhile, backward change is a shift in circumstances that has a bad influence on society. The cause of this change is due to internal factors, namely an increasing or decreasing population, new discoveries, and conflicts in society. In addition, there are also external factors due to the influence of the surrounding environment, other cultures, and wars.

Nowadays, technology is developing so fast that it can change people's lives, and the world of animal husbandry is no exception. In the livestock sector, we can see various changes in behaviour that occur. If we look at the efficiency, of course this is very efficient because it can save time and energy. However, if we look at it from the social side, it has a bad impact because if previously for breeding various examples of changes in the livestock sector are changes in behaviour that have a big impact on society. Every change and development that exists must have a good and bad impact depending on which side we look at it. The good impact of the development of technology is usually related to farming activities that have become much easier, more efficient and modern. But on the other hand, there is a bad impact that lurks, namely the increasingly tenuous interaction between communities, as well as many people

who lose their jobs because they are replaced by machines. To overcome this, we must be able to always keep up with the development of existing technology, but still must not forget or eliminate jobs for the surrounding community. The government in this case needs to organise advocacy so that the community is more directed and organised in accordance with the information SR informant said:

“The library manager actively advocates to the village government to get support in the form of funds and library facilities and infrastructure. Cooperation support from other parties also encouraged the change, such as youth and cross-sector activities carried out in the library” (Interview 13 August 2023)

This is in line with informant RM said:

“I found out about the village library because I often visited the village office to take care of other activities, where I saw that there was a room in which there was a shelf with books that were irregularly arranged, still messy as if they were not used. I then went to the village head, asking permission to tidy up and manage the books in the library. From there, I was empowered to manage the village library” (Interview 13 August 2023)

Previous studies have shown that one method of building community literacy is through public libraries. The existence of a village library is a means to support the process of forming a smart community and a community that has a high interest in reading. The public library has a strategic position in the community around the public library because the library is tasked with collecting, managing and providing knowledge records to be read and studied. With the existence of a public library, the surrounding community will be helped in accessing the information they need.

The purpose of the library is to help people of all ages by providing opportunities and encouragement through library services so that they: 1) Can educate themselves continuously; 2) Can be responsive to advances in various fields of science, social and political life; 3) Can maintain constructive freedom of thought to become better members of the family and society; 4) Can develop creative thinking skills, foster spirituality and can use their abilities to be able to appreciate the results of human art and culture; 5) Can improve the level of daily life and employment; 6) Can become a good citizen and can participate actively in national development and in fostering mutual understanding between nations; and 7) Can make good use of leisure time that is beneficial for personal and social life. One of the villages in Maros Regency that has successfully established and developed a public library is Pajukukang Village in Bontoa Sub-district. The public library, named "Al-Iqra" Library, won first place in the village and library competition at the district level in 2019 and at the national level in 2020 organized by the National Library of Indonesia. Al-Iqra Library successfully built a network of partnership cooperation with various stakeholders.

Various community empowerment programmers have been successfully carried out to improve the standard of living and welfare of the community through sustainable community training programmers. This is the excellence of this library so that it is able to become the best public library in Maros in 2019 and in Indonesia in 2020. Basically, the library must have shortcomings, whether from services, facilities, and others. To find out what are the shortcomings of the library and also what expectations the community wants from the library, an evaluation of the library is needed. Revitalization is part of the efforts used by the library as a means to be better in the future [13].

This is in accordance with informant NA said:

“Yes, there is additional income. Sales from raising ducks are very helpful, although not too big a result, at least it can be an additional income. The results obtained from the sale of ducks amounted to 300 thousand, at least helping the income of my husband who has a business making and selling culverts” (Interview 1 October 2023)

Thus SI affirmed the role of libraries in encouraging behavioural change among farmers in Maros said:

“Knowledge about farming techniques was initially obtained from SI's neighbour who regularly visited the village library to obtain information about duck farming techniques. From Pak Sahir's information, I then attended counselling at the village library. After attending the library counselling, I then developed the duck breeding business, which was just a hobby, into a profitable side business. At the library I was also shown through the computer how to breed ducks” (Interview 1 October 2023)

Based on the activities carried out, namely Improving the Al-Iqra Library in Pajukukang Village, Bontoa District, Maros, it can be concluded that good library management will make people interested in visiting the library to read. By reading, villagers can gain new knowledge and skills that can later change their behaviour to be more productive.

As mentioned earlier, that the transformation of the library based on social inclusion is a form of library as lifelong learning where the library is not only a centre of information sources but more than that as a place to transform itself as a socio-cultural centre by empowering and democratising society and local communities, in an effort to improve the welfare of the community, especially the people in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency in accordance with the statement of SR:

“The village library provides information on farming techniques through counselling activities, through books available in the village library, and also watching YouTube about good duck farming techniques. The library provides books, computers and Smart TVs that can be used by the community to obtain information. In addition to counselling conducted in the library, the library manager also provides assistance in the community after counselling activities are carried out, or conducts direct discussions with farmers” (Interview 1 September 2023)

This is also according to RM:

“I have a side job as a pond farmer, by being entrusted as a library manager, I read many books on how to manage ponds so that the results are maximised. In 2019 the library was transformed into a social inclusion-based library by receiving assistance from the national library in the form of computers, printers, books and shelves. With these facilities, it is easier for me to search through YouTube about the technicalities of managing ponds. I then socialised the village library to the general public, anyone can come to the library, students, people with disabilities, the elderly, housewives etc. (Interview 1 November 2023)

The library is not only an information centre but also a social inclusion-based library transforming itself as a socio-cultural centre in improving the economic welfare of its citizens to create a prosperous community through the library. The availability of quality information and access is needed but the inability of residents in Pajukukang Village to obtain information due to lack of education and access to information.

Increasing access to information, strengthening information infrastructure in strengthening the context of information for individuals ultimately forms citizens who do not know to know so that information justice in improving information literacy with the existence of a social inclusion-based library can improve the economic welfare of Pajukukan residents of Maros Regency. Improving welfare through library utilisation is the first library activity of the national library. The library in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency has a role to support priority activities to strengthen literacy, especially in the field of animal husbandry. The existence of a social inclusion-based library in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency encourages people to be able to raise good livestock in order to produce good livestock products. Social inclusion-based libraries are libraries that proactively help individuals and communities to develop skills and confidence, and help improve social networks.

Libraries also support communities, adults and families to learn in social inclusion libraries. Libraries that facilitate people in developing their potential by looking at cultural diversity, willingness to accept change, and offering business opportunities, protecting and fighting for culture and human rights can be said to be social inclusion-based libraries. This is in accordance with the opinion of informant RM:

“At first, I thought that by giving expensive food to livestock, I could get good results, but it was not to be. After I attended the training from this library, I learned that livestock do not need to be given expensive food but only with leftover food, the results of my livestock are much better and when selling the price is also good” (Interview 1 November 2023)

Pajukukang Village Library has successfully implemented a social inclusion-based library transformation, which makes it a place for learning and joint activities through community empowerment. Community empowerment activities that have been successfully carried out aim to improve the quality of life of the community and improve community welfare through community engagement activities that are carried out in a sustainable manner and have an impact on the community around the village library. Pajukukang Village Library in implementing community empowerment activities also builds cooperation networks with various parties to carry out activities that benefit the community, and has good library management.

CONCLUSION

Change is an ongoing process in every society. There is a process of change that runs in such a way that it is not felt by the supporting community. Such a movement of change is called evolution. Sociology has an overview of the evolutionary changes in society from simple society to modern society. The process of motion of change is in a range of goals into modern society. This happens because modern society is a form of society that aspires to have a good and more perfect label, such as progress, humanity, and civilisation. The behavioural changes that occur from a simple society towards a modern society take place slowly, without destroying the foundations that build society, so it takes a long time. One of the factors that influence behaviour

change is the increase in public knowledge that can be obtained through education and reading. The role of the library as a medium for public learning is important in the process of behaviour change. This study was conducted in Pajukukang Village, Maros Regency to examine the role of libraries in increasing knowledge and new skills for villagers, which in turn can change their behaviour. The research shows that the library can inspire villagers to start a duck farming business thanks to the books they read in the village library. Thus, the village library, which provides knowledge to the villagers, functions as a tool to trigger behaviour change.

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